

ИЗМЕНЕНИЕ СЕМАНТИКИ ЛЕКСЕМЫ “PAROLE” В КАНАДСКИХ ПРАВОВЫХ ТЕКСТАХ**THE SEMANTIC CHANGE OF THE LEXEME “PAROLE” IN CANADIAN LEGAL TEXTS****НУДЕЛЬМАН МАРИЯ АЛЕКСАНДРОВНА,***кандидат филологических наук,
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В предложенной статье рассматривается изменение семантики лексемы “parole” в канадском варианте английского языка на основе историко-фактологического материала правовых текстов разных столетий. Вслед за выяснением этимологии данной лексемы настоящее исследование осуществляется путём разделения правовых текстов Канады по времени их возникновения на два периода: XVIII-XIX века и XX-XXI века соответственно. Методика диахронического анализа позволила сделать выводы о развитии дополнительных значений лексемы “parole”, не нашедших свое отражение в словаре, но намечающих перспективу дальнейшего развития этого слова.

The article deals with the semantic change of the lexeme “parole” in Canadian English on the basis of historical and factual material of legal texts of different II centuries. After the etymology of this lexeme has been found out, the research is carried out by the division of Canadian legal texts into two periods, such as the 18th-19th centuries and the 20th-21st centuries respectively. With the help of the technique of diachronic analysis, the author comes to the conclusion that some additional meanings of the lexeme “parole” have been developed. They are not fixed in dictionaries yet, but show the prospect for further development.

Ключевые слова: лексема, семантика, правовые тексты Канады, концептуальная доминанта, досрочное освобождение.

Key words: lexeme, semantics, Canadian legal texts, conceptual dominant, parole.

В данной статье мы предлагаем обратиться к анализу семантики лексемы “parole” при её функционировании в правовых текстах Канады XVIII-XXI веков, что является одним из этапов изучения языковой репрезентации концептуальной доминанты «освобождение от наказания» в канадском варианте английского языка.

Какими значениями обладало это слово на протяжении стольких лет? Охарактеризуем лексему “parole” с точки зрения её этимологии.

Слово “parole” в 1610–20 годах имело значение «слово чести». Как выяснилось, в XVIII веке оно приобрело значение «пароль, используемый офицером или инспектором охраны». Происходит от старофранцузского слова “parole” в значении «официальное обещание» [6; 21]. Первоначально отмечалось использование народно-латинской формы **paraula* в значении «речь, дискурс», а также *parabola* с тем же значением в латинском языке. Интересу-

ющее нас значение «условное освобождение заключенного перед полным отбытием срока наказания» впервые было зафиксировано в 1908 году в преступном сленге [7].

Существует мнение о том, что эта лексема появилась гораздо раньше - в XV веке (1470-80 годах) [20]. Наряду с этим отмечается предположение о том, что лексема появилась в другое время, а именно в 1531 году [8].

Для исследования семантики лексемы “parole” в диахроническом аспекте предлагаем разделить правовые тексты Канады по времени их возникновения на два периода: XVIII-XIX века и XX-XXI века соответственно.

Проанализируем семантику этой лексемы при её функционировании в правовых текстах Канады XVIII-XIX веков. Лексема “parole” обладает следующими словарными значениями:

– Разрешение, данное заключённому, покинуть тюрьму досрочно, если он обещал подчиняться определённым правилам / освобождение заключённого перед тем, как срок действия его или её приговора закончился, при условии, что он или она отличается хорошим поведением;

The villagers were released on parole, and for three days he waited in anxiety and prayer, not knowing whether the issue would be life or death. The villagers passed him with averted faces, as if blaming him for their threatened ruin, and he imagined that he could read reproaches in his own men's eyes [22].

– Условное освобождение из места лишения свободы или другого тюремного заключения после того, как часть наказания уже была отбита;

Whereas, two certain Ordinances were made and passed on the twenty fourth day of February in the thirty second year of His Majesty's reign the one intituled “An Ordinance relating to Causes in appeal to the Court of the Governor and Executive Council” the other intituled “An Ordinance to facilitate the productions of parole proof in civil causes” which said Ordinance as temporary Ordinances will lose their force unless provision be made for continuing the same [10].

– Период, когда заключённый, который освобождён, должен продолжать подчиняться конкретным правилам;

It was stated that the prisoner came to deliver himself up the following morning, having been allowed that time upon parole, that he went to Mr. J.S. Morse, who held the judgment against him, that Mr. Morse said he had given no instructions to issue an execution, and directed his release which was granted, that Mr. Hunter then went to the Prothonotary of the court to ascertain if any execution had been issued, and at what time, and that the Prothonotary told him the execution was issued near dark, the night before being the twenty-seventh day of August [15].

– Обещание, данное заключённым, хорошо себя вести, если ему даруют свободу или нестрогие условия заключения.

I have received the three letters which you did me honor to write to me on the 6th, 13th and 18th of June last. I had been obliged, My Lord, in order to make you understand what I meant when I had the honor to ask of you a declaration securing the ownership of the lands to those in possession of them, to insert these words: “in virtue of any title whatever,” and for this purpose I had the honor to explain to you, by my letter of the 10th November last, that many inhabitants of this country had obtained grants of land on simple tickets; others have nothing in their favor but possession on the verbal promise (sur la parole) of the seigniors; others again have lost or mislaid these tickets [3].

Итак, в канадских правовых текстах XVIII-XIX веков отмечается присутствие словарных значений лексемы “parole”, к разряду которых относятся: разрешение, данное заключённому, покинуть тюрьму досрочно, если он обещал подчиняться определённым правилам / освобождение заключённого перед тем, как срок действия его или её приговора закончился при условии, что он или она отличается хорошим поведением; условное освобождение из

места лишения свободы или другого тюремного заключения после того, как часть наказания уже была отбыта; период, когда заключённый, который освобождён, должен продолжать подчиняться конкретным правилам; обещание, данное заключённым, хорошо себя вести, если ему даруют свободу или нестрогие условия заключения.

Обратимся к анализу современных текстов Канады. В них нашли своё отражение следующие словарные значения лексемы “parole”:

– Разрешение, данное заключённому, покинуть тюрьму досрочно, если он обещал подчиняться определённым правилам / освобождение заключённого перед тем, как срок действия его или её приговора закончился, при условии, что он или она отличается хорошим поведением;

*Both sections 102 and 126 deal with criteria for an accused being released on **parole**, not the criteria for suspension of **parole**. Nevertheless, the Applicant opines that it is inconsistent that those who commit murder or an offence set out in Schedule 1 can conceivably be released under section 102, whereas he asserts that is not permitted in section 126(2). He asserts that the mere possibility of any offence, even a traffic ticket could disentitle a release under section 102 but only the possibility of violence disentitles under section 126. From that he argues that “undue risk to society” is vague and overbroad. He is correct that the tests are different but I disagree they are inconsistent. Then he goes to paragraph 134(1):*

*Instructions to Released Offenders (1) – An offender who has been released on parole, statutory release or unescorted temporary absence shall comply with any instructions given by a member of the Board or a person designated, by name or by position, by the Chairperson of the Board or the Commissioner, or given by the institutional head, or by the offender’s parole supervisor, respecting any conditions of **parole**, statutory release or unescorted temporary absence in order to prevent a breach of any condition or to protect society [5].*

– Условное освобождение из места лишения свободы или другого тюремного заключения после того, как часть наказания уже была отбыта;

*Section 25 of the Penitentiary Act by its terms only operates once an inmate is placed on **parole**. This section in such event requires in the computation of length of **parole** the inclusion of statutory remission credited to the inmate at the time of his release on **parole**. The purpose of this provision would appear to be to permit the continuation of the supervision of the parolee while at large for the entire term of the sentence imposed [12].*

– Период, когда заключённый, который освобождён, должен продолжать подчиняться конкретным правилам;

*On March 6, 1959, the appellant was convicted of manslaughter and sentenced to a 25-year term of imprisonment that was to expire on March 5, 1984. He subsequently benefited from an amnesty of 750 days that brought forward the date of expiration of his sentence to February 14, 1982. In June 1965 he was released on **parole**, which was revoked on December 21, 1966. The revocation resulted in deferring the end of his sentence to April 15, 1983, since, at that time, under subsection 20(1) of the Act [S.C. 1958, c. 38], the time spent on **parole** was not deducted from the duration of the term of imprisonment if the **parole** was revoked. In other words, an inmate in such circumstances was deemed not to have served his sentence of detention during his **parole** period that was subsequently revoked [14].*

– Обещание, данное заключённым, хорошо себя вести, если ему даруют свободу или нестрогие условия заключения.

*Mr. Johnny submits that there was no basis for revoking his **parole**. He submits that he was obviously doing well on **parole** as a contributing member of the community, and that the allegations of criminal conduct have no evidence to support them. Mr. Johnny says that in revoking his **parole** the Board dealt with him as though he were the Ivon Johnny of the 1980s, and not the Ivon Johnny of today, who has made a lot of changes [9].*

Кроме словарных значений изучаемую концептуальную доминанту «освобождение от наказания» в канадском варианте английского языка способны репрезентировать такие контекстуальные значения, как:

- Уловно-досрочное освобождение как привилегия;

*Per Judson, Ritchie, Pigeon and Beetz JJ.: The essence of **parole** is that it is a privilege accorded to certain prisoners in the discretion of the Parole Board and not a right to which all prison inmates are entitled. The Parole Board is a statutory body clothed with an unfettered discretion in the administration of the Parole Act and is not bound to act on a judicial or quasi-judicial basis. The very nature of the task assigned to the Board makes it necessary that it be clothed with as wide a discretion as possible and that its decision should not be open to question on appeal or otherwise be subject to the same procedures as those which accompany the review of decision of a judicial or quasi-judicial tribunal [13].*

- Преждевременное условно-досрочное освобождение из тюремного заключения;

*So the acceptable range for parole ineligibility must be regarded as being set primarily for the purpose of continuing denunciation of a rehabilitated person. I suppose individual judges will have their own views about what a civilised society should demand as the appropriate measure of retribution and denunciation. The function of this Court is to try to achieve a measure of consistency in that respect. And, again, in exercising their function in relation to consistency, both the sentencing judge and this Court must bear in mind that the years of parole ineligibility are real 365 day years and not, as in the case of other sentences, years that are subject to reduction through statutory release and early **parole** [16].*

- Полное условно-досрочное освобождение;

*On June 1, 1983, Mr. Armaly was convicted of second-degree murder and sentenced to life imprisonment. He was subsequently released on full **parole** on August 12, 1997, subject to conditions which included one that he abstain from using intoxicants. Upon release from prison Mr. Armaly relocated to Edmonton to pursue employment. He ended up with sporadic employment and unstable living arrangements which together resulted in numerous moves. In February 1999, Mr. Armaly requested residency at Independence Apartments Community Residential Facility ("CRF"), a half-way house in Edmonton. One month later he moved to Didsbury to pursue vocational education. Mr. Armaly enrolled in a course and earned his Heavy Equipment Operator ticket. In spite of this further qualification he was still unable to find employment sufficient to support himself. He returned to Independence Apartments and began to receive Employment Insurance benefits [1].*

- Частичное условно-досрочное освобождение;

*I now turn to the equivalent provisions under the former Act. Section 2 of the Parole Act defined "parole" as the "authority granted under this Act to an inmate to be at large during the inmate's term of imprisonment and includes day **parole**". Section 2 of the Parole Regulations defined "full parole" as "parole other than day **parole**". The section also defined "eligibility date" as "the date on which an inmate has completed serving the portion of the term of imprisonment required to be served by that inmate in accordance with these regulations before full parole, day **parole** or temporary absence, as the case may be, may be granted or authorized" [4].*

- Условно-досрочное освобождение как система;

*The sentencing and **parole** regimes have different functions and spheres of responsibility, but they do not exist in separate watertight compartments. Changes to the **parole** regime enacted through amendments to the CCRA are not for that reason alone incapable of imposing or increasing the "punishment" inherent in the sentences offenders serve [11].*

- Соответствующие властные структуры, имеющие полномочие досрочно освободить преступника из тюремного заключения;

If either the petitioner or the parole authorities were correct, the Board was without jurisdiction to make a mandatory supervision order. The order itself was conditioned upon a positive community assessment on a couple living in Abbotsford, which was not forthcoming. Thus the petitioner was told he would have a full detention hearing the following day. The next day, which was March 8th, the petitioner was advised that the matter was to be set over for a full hearing because the Board had obtained information which indicated to it that the petitioner is likely to commit an offence causing the death of or serious harm to another person before his warrant expiry date. This new information appeared to have cured any deficiency of evidence to support their finding that s. 21.3(2) (c) had been met, which was the subsection dealing with the likelihood of causing serious harm or death [19].

– Статус преступника, получившего условно-досрочное освобождение;

The Applicant, Mr. Richard Chiu, was released on Full Parole on July 4, 2003. Subsequently, however, his parole has been revoked. He disputes the revocation of his parole and, in an apparent attempt to regain Full Parole status, brought an application for judicial review of a letter, written on July 4, 2005, by S. Réhel, an employee of the NPB Appeal Division [2].

- ходатайство преступника о получении условно-досрочного освобождения;

One of the grievor's responsibilities, for which she was trained, was to replenish the supply of parole application kits as quantities dwindled. The grievor was to order the kits from a printer with an appropriate sequence number. Without informing Ms. Harty or Mr. Bellefeuille, the grievor delegated the monitoring of the number of application kits on hand to a pardons officer. The grievor delayed ordering the kits because apparently she was waiting for the approval of the user fee increase. The grievor was unable to locate the blueprints from the previous printing. She misunderstood the numbering sequence, and no amount of explanation by Mr. Bellefeuille made her understand the mathematics of ordering sequential forms. Mr. Bellefeuille had to remind her about retrieving the kits from the temporary storage area once they arrived from the printer [18].

– Условно-досрочное освобождение без возражений.

Mr. Tao raises three grounds of appeal in relation to his sentence, but all three grounds relate to the fact that his sentence of 13 years and 8 months' imprisonment makes him ineligible for parole for a longer period than if he had received a life sentence. This arises from the provisions of s. 120 of the Corrections and Conditional Release Act, S.C. 1992, c. 20, and the fact that pre-sentence custody is part of the sentence for a life sentence that has been served, while pre-sentence custody for a non-life sentence is not taken into account in determining parole eligibility. Under s. 120(1) of the Corrections and Conditional Release Act, Mr. Tao was not eligible for parole until he had served the lesser of one-third of his sentence and seven years; namely, 4 years and 6 2/3rds months. If he had been given a life sentence, he would have been eligible for parole under s. 120(2) of the Corrections and Conditional Release Act after he had served 7 years less the amount of his pre-sentence custody; namely, 3 years and 10 months [17].

Итак, в современных правовых текстах Канады концептуальную доминанту «освобождение от наказания» репрезентируют словарные значения лексемы “parole” типа: разрешение, данное заключённому, покинуть тюрьму досрочно, если он обещал подчиняться определённым правилам / освобождение заключённого перед тем, как срок действия его или её приговора закончился при условии, что он или она отличается хорошим поведением; условное освобождение из места лишения свободы или другого тюремного заключения после того, как часть наказания уже была отбыта; период, когда заключённый, который освобождён, должен продолжать подчиняться конкретным правилам; обещание, данное заключённым, хорошо себя вести, если ему даруют свободу или нестрогие условия заключения. Кроме этого, данную доминанту могут выражать в тексте такие контекстуальные значения лексемы, как: условно-досрочное освобождение как привилегия; преждевременное условно-досрочное освобождение из тюремного заключения; полное условно-досрочное освобождение; частичное условно-досрочное освобождение; условно-досрочное освобождение как система; власт-

ные структуры, имеющие полномочие досрочно освободить преступника из тюремного заключения; статус преступника, получившего условно-досрочное освобождение; ходатайство преступника о получении условно-досрочного освобождения; условно-досрочное освобождение без возражений.

Сравнение показывает, что словарные значения этой лексемы, перечисленные выше, представляющие изучаемую концептуальную доминанту в правовых текстах Канады, обладают устойчивостью и употребительностью. Появившиеся контекстуальные значения на данный момент в словаре не отражены и намечают перспективу дальнейшего развития семантики этой лексемы при экспликации исследуемой концептуальной доминанты в канадских правовых текстах.

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